

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KACHO TAH****FIRST NAME: CHARLES****PROGRAM CODE: DSDD****COURSE CODE : ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. KABIRU GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 4%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR COURSE ACA-401D

1. Which of the following sentences about reading and researching your topic for an academic essay is correct?

- Reading and researching your topic will give the knowledge and evidence to develop a thesis and answer.¹**
- Reading and researching your topic help keep the topic or question of the essay clearly in mind to avoid change of topic with insights acquired from literature.
- Reading and researching your topic help document the names of authors and publication information.

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*, Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 8.

- Reading and researching your topic help focus only on sources that support your argument, as the purpose is to back the argument.
2. Which of the following sentences best describes an introduction in an academic essay?
- An introduction begins with general and then narrows down to specifics, starts with a broad opening statement of the topic area, and then the thesis statement and ends with a summary or road map of the essay.²**
- An introduction begins with general and then narrows down to specifics, starts with a broad opening statement of the topic area, and then the thesis statement and ends with implications for future research.
- An introduction moves from specific to general, recapping the answer to the research question and the main points of an argument and ending with implications and opportunities for further research related to the subject without introducing new information or knowledge.
- An introduction comprises paragraphs that develop your argument using the evidence gathered and conclusions from your arguments.
3. Which of the following statements about academic research is valid?
- Academic research addresses conceptual problems, specifically limitations to understanding situations.³**

² Cleenewerck and Gulma, 10.

³ Kate Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Student Writers and Researchers*, Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018), 22.

- Academic research addresses practical problems such as how to address insomnia, falling profits, and climate change.
 - Academic research aims to conclude a topic rather than keep a critical conversation going.
 - Academic research that is rigorous enough does not have to raise any more questions on the topic.
4. Which one of the following sentences about identifying and reading your sources is correct:
- Thorough and critical reading, including sources beyond your selected sources, is crucial to understanding and responding to an essential or controversial source.⁴**
 - Thorough and critical reading without taking notes is advised because there are often many sources to review.
 - Thorough and critical reading means focusing mainly on sources that contradict your hypothesis so you might find a way to foster your argument.
 - Thorough and critical reading is often unnecessary, especially for sources that challenge your position and deter you from your argument.
5. Which statement best represents the five elements of an argument in the correct order?
- claim, reason, evidence, acknowledgment and response, and warrant⁵**

⁴ Turabian, 46.

⁵ Turabian, 58.

- claim, hypothesis, question, acknowledgment and response, and warrant
- claim, reason, hypothesis, acknowledgment and response, and warrant
- claim, reason, question, acknowledgment and response, and warrant
- claim, hypothesis, evidence, acknowledgment and response, and warrant

6. Which of the following note citations of a book is correct?

- Charles Tah and Victor Mbinda, *Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Effective Social Performance Management (Antwerp: Antwerp University Press, 2013), 12-13.*⁶**
- Charles Tah and Victor Mbinda. Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Effective Social Performance Management (Antwerp: Antwerp University Press, 2013), 12-13.
- Tah Charles and Victor Mbinda, Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Social Effective Performance Management (Antwerp: Antwerp University Press, 2013), 12-13.
- Charles Tah and Victor Mbinda, Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Social Effective Performance Management (Antwerp: Antwerp University Press, 2013), 12-13.

7. Which of the bibliography entries below of a journal article is correct?

⁶ Turabian, 171.

- Tah, Charles and Victor Mbinda. “Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Social Performance Management.” *The Economist* 46, no. 3 (September 2013): 171-185. [https://doi.org/ 10.1033/686775](https://doi.org/10.1033/686775).⁷
 - Charles Tah and Victor Mbinda, “Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Social Performance Management,” *The Economist* 46, no. 3 (September 2013): 171-185, [https://doi.org/ 10.1033/686775](https://doi.org/10.1033/686775).
 - Tah, Charles and Victor Mbinda. 2013. “Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Social Performance Management.” *The Economist* 46, no. 3 (September): 171-185. [https://doi.org/ 10.1033/686775](https://doi.org/10.1033/686775).
 - Tah, Charles and Victor Mbinda. “Financial Cooperative Governance: Perspectives for Social Performance Management.” *The Economist* 46, no. 3 (September 2013): 171-185. [https://doi.org/ 10.1033/686775](https://doi.org/10.1033/686775).
8. Chose the bullet point that corresponds to the four components or documents in the correct order that students complete as part of dissertation research:
- dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript**⁸
 - dissertation prospectus, dissertation concept paper, dissertation, and dissertation manuscript

⁷ Turabian, 190.

⁸ James Sampson, *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*, Second Edition (Florida: Florida State University, 2017), 2.

- dissertation manuscript, dissertation concept paper, dissertation prospectus, and dissertation
- dissertation concept paper, dissertation manuscript, dissertation prospectus, and dissertation

9. Why are readers keen on the method of research?

- To judge if the method adequately examines the research question and hypothesis.**⁹
- To compare with the methods used in other research on the topic.
- To identify limitations that the researcher has been unable to identify to devalue the work.
- To check if the analysis and findings are coherent with the method.

10. Which of the following best represents the chapters of a dissertation?

- Introduction, Literature Review, Method, Findings, Discussions, and Conclusion.**¹⁰
- Abstract, Introduction, Literature Review, Method, Findings, Discussions, and Conclusion.
- Abstract, Introduction, Background, Method, Findings and Discussion, and Conclusion.
- Introduction, Research Question, Method, Findings, Discussions, and Conclusion.

⁹ Sampson, 34.

¹⁰ Sampson, 66–77.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition. Bangui: Euclid University, 2021.
- Sampson, James. *A Guide to Quantitative and Qualitative Dissertation Research*. Second Edition. Florida: Florida State University, 2017.
- Turabian, Kate. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Thesis, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Student Writers and Researchers*. Ninth Edition. Chicago and London: The University of Chicago Press, 2018.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.